

ISic1017

I.Sicily inscription 1017

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacombs

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [ένθά]δε κίτε Ζ[ωσίμη]
2. [ήκαλῆς] μνήμης νύμφη
3. [Ἰουβί]νου ζήσασα ἔτη κβ
4. [τελευτᾶ]πρὸ] ιζ καλαν
5. [δῶν ---]ν □

Apparatus

Text after Ferrua 1946-1947, 236 no. 38

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492644

EDCS 39102171

PHI 140495

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0197 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Carini, I. 1873. Iscrizioni rinvenute nelle Catacombe di Siracusa. *Archivio Storico Siciliano*. 1: 260-263. At 261

Ferrua, A 1946-1947. Florilegio d'iscrizioni paleocristiane di Sicilia. *Rendiconti della Pontifica accademia romana di archeologia*. 22: 227-239. At 236, no.38

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